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"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

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Gender Employment Gap of the Indigenous Population in Canadian AI-related Industries

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Background and Purpose

Artificial intelligence (AI) has impacted numerous industries over the past decades and caused workforce disruptions. It is claimed that up to 70% of companies will be able to actively use at least one type of AI technology in their processes by 2030 and that this shift could produce an additional \$16 trillion in global economic growth by 2030 or result in a 16% increase in aggregate GDP compared to today's level (Karpunina et al., 2020). Canada's interest in AI follows the global trend, with the government charging the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research to develop and lead a \$125 million Pan-Canadian Artificial Intelligence Strategy, the world's first national AI strategy. Since the program's initiation in 2017, it has produced a 3.6% growth in tech employment, \$658 million in venture capital funding to Canadian AI start-ups, and over 45 new AI R&D labs established by major multinational firms (CIFAR, 2020).

However, despite these initiatives inducing a vast industrial impact, there is a lack of consideration for the possible negative socio-economic impacts on Canadian citizens. In this article, we aim to study the socio-economic divide of the AI workforce in Canadian society with regard to the Indigenous population and also provide some analysis regarding gender. This article, therefore, seeks to answer three main questions: (1) What are the industries associated with Canadian companies involved in AI-related R&D? (2) What percentage of the Indigenous population is employed by these industries? (3) What is the gender gap in employment of the Indigenous population compared to that of the non-Indigenous population?

We approach these research questions by conducting a bibliometric analysis of AI-related patents and publications, mapping the companies involved in the production of AI technology while examining the distribution of the Indigenous population and women in the industries where these companies are located.

Methods

In this study, we use patent assignee data to identify Canadian companies involved in developing AI-related inventions. AI-related patents are extracted from the United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO) database, using the US Class 706 (Data Processing - Artificial Intelligence) and its concordance to IPC8 subclasses¹. The data is confined to AI-related utility patents granted to Canadian companies or corporations in 2007-2020. To determine the primary industries where these companies are located, we associate companies with their primary North American Industry Classification System (NAICS) code using the *Mergent intellect* and *Mergent online* company information databases. As a result, we assigned the NAICS code to 297 (out of 359) companies and 1152 (out of 1271) patents. These industries are further assigned to Statistics Canada's employment information by Indigenous and Non-Indigenous populations² (Statistics Canada, 2022), which provides the list of industries, their subsequent NAICS code, and the number of Indigenous and Non-Indigenous populations employed in Canada in those industries since 2007. Employment data are further assigned to the companies at the time of granting to capture the socio-economic characteristic and ensure that the company was active. Accordingly, the employment data are defined by both the number of patents and the primary industry of the companies involved in AI-related inventions. The employment rate is identified by dividing the number of persons employed in each Indigenous identity group by the total number of persons employed. We further calculate the gender gap in employment as the difference between men and women employed to that of men, and also the average employment rate and gender gap at the level of all industries from 2007 to 2020. This time period was selected for our study as AI was on its third major historical rise (Kersting, 2020) and demonstrated exponential involvement in leading industries. We then compare the employment rate and gender gap of AI-infused industries by Indigenous population (total), as well as the Indigenous groups of Métis and First Nations to those of all Canadian industries.

Table 1 reveals the share of AI-related industrial patents and their assignees by industry.

Table 1- Share of AI-related industrial patents and their assignees by industry

Top industries [NAICS code]	Companies	Patents
Professional, scientific and technical services [54]	39%	23%
Manufacturing [31-33]	20%	48%
Information, culture and recreation [51, 71]	18%	10%
Wholesale and retail trade [41, 44-45]	8%	10%
Business, building and other support services [55-56]	7%	4%
Finance, insurance, real estate, rental and leasing [52-53]	4%	3%
Transportation and warehousing [48-49]	2%	1%

¹ Available at: <https://www.uspto.gov/web/patents/classification/uspc706/us706toipc8.htm>

² The Indigenous population includes "persons who reported having an Indigenous identity, that is, First Nations (North American Indian), Métis or Inuk (Inuit) or those who reported more than one identity. Excluded from the survey's coverage are persons living on reserves and other Indigenous settlements in the provinces, as well as those living in the territories. Data on persons reporting being Inuit or having multiple identities are included in the Indigenous total but are not shown separately because of small sample sizes" (Statistics Canada, 2021). The non-Indigenous population is the population that did not identify with any of the Indigenous groups (First Nations, Métis, Inuit); did not indicate Registered or Treaty Indian Status, nor indicated band membership (Statistics Canada, 2021).

Findings

This study reveals that Indigenous groups' employment rate in AI-related industries is 1.3 times lower than in all industries (Table 2). At the same time, no such difference is found with the non-Indigenous population. This study also shows that the gender gap in employment is 33% higher in AI-related industries than the average gender gap in employment in the Canadian economy. Also, this difference is higher for the Indigenous population (Table 3).

Table 2- Employment rate by Indigenous and non-Indigenous population in AI-related and all industries and their difference

	Employment rate (AI)	Employment rate (All)	Difference (AI minus All)
First Nations			
Both sexes	0.98%	1.31%	-0.33%
Females	1.08%	1.40%	-0.32%
Males	0.92%	1.22%	-0.30%
Indigenous population (total)			
Both sexes	2.14%	2.89%	-0.75%
Females	2.28%	3.02%	-0.74%
Males	2.06%	2.76%	-0.70%
Métis			
Both sexes	1.12%	1.52%	-0.39%
Females	1.16%	1.55%	-0.39%
Males	1.10%	1.49%	-0.38%
Non-Indigenous population			
Both sexes	97.86%	97.11%	0.75%
Females	97.72%	96.98%	0.74%
Males	97.94%	97.24%	0.70%

Table 3- The gender gap in employment by Indigenous groups in AI-related and all industries and their difference

Group	AI	All	Difference (AI minus All)
First Nations	33%	-4%	37%
Indigenous population	37%	1%	36%
Métis	37%	1%	36%
Non-Indigenous population	43%	10%	33%
Total population	43%	10%	33%

Conclusion and Discussions

This study shows that the Indigenous population is underrepresented in AI-related industries and that the gender gap in employment for this population is more evident than in other groups. The exclusion of this community in AI work could cause implicit user biases in AI-based products, a deficiency of vital perspectives to guide software design, and the absence of valuable knowledge that could aid in resolving ethical dilemmas. This study is one of the first that sheds light on the impact of technology on indigenization and can serve as a baseline to mainstream equity, diversity, and inclusion policies in AI research and development discourse.

Research Limitations and Future Research

It is vital to mention that our research is subject to some limitations, mainly regarding the Census data provided by Statistics Canada. This resource mentions that the survey does not include all types of current jobs in Canada, nor does it properly represent all communities³. Therefore, our study is restricted to the inclusion of the identities listed in the Census questionnaire.

This study analyzes the industries in which Canadian companies involved in AI-related research and development (R&D) operate. As illustrated, patents are just one key indicator for identifying R&D in the industrial setting. For future research, we would like to include scientific publications between the same time period to determine which organizations have had influence over the development of AI technology over these years.

Also, we would like to expand our research to consider how these industries are inclusive for women, the Indigenous population, older adults and the ageing population, and the intersections of these groups of people and incorporate other socio-economic attributes, such as the labour force, employment, full-time employment, part-time employment, unemployment and unemployment rate, union coverage, job permanency, employment by establishment size, working overtime, multiple job-holding and wage rate, in order to draw more insights towards technological advancements power on Canadian society.

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³ More information can be found here: <https://www12.statcan.gc.ca/census-recensement/2021/ref/98-26-0001/2020001/007-eng.cfm?fbclid=IwAR33uIM2K7hYsbrc5xRDqqKj-xbbd7lshMgC7fHM8CGA7gaNCUBpj17pRIw>

